

CREATIVE
INFORMATICS

CREATIVE INFORMATICS
FINAL REPORT 2018-2024

OPEN
LIVE
HOPE
THINGS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Director's Report

It is always hard to look back at a long-term programme and try to distil it but, in the case of Creative Informatics, looking back at a programme so fast-moving and agile gives me a wonderful sense of vertigo and astonishment. As one of the original writers of the proposal that turned into the funded Creative Cluster, I've been working on Creative Informatics since 2017. I have many fond memories and am incredibly proud of everything we have achieved together.

Community is front and centre of this final Project Report. When, in 2018, we got the fateful call (well, text message) to say that we had been successful in winning funding, I knew that we needed to build a community that spanned Edinburgh and its regions and that bridged the technology and creative sectors. If we managed to do that successfully, the community would live on long after any funded period of the grant, and the legacy would be the connections made, the sparks ignited and the creation of a new creative-tech social infrastructure that would support this marvellous city and its institutions, SMEs, freelancers and researchers.

In response to everything we threw at them, this community has been fantastic. Through 40 funding calls and hundreds of events, labs, and socials, we built a network that navigated a pandemic and innovated through a time of economic crisis. Later on in this report you will see details of the Gross Value Added that Creative Informatics produced for the local economy: together we grew £10m from four different funders to an eye-watering £78.5m, creating 212 new products, services and experiences, 47 new spin-outs and 445 new and safeguarded jobs along the way. We couldn't have done this without the passion and support of the 2637 individuals from across the creative industries that were willing to be trained, supported, enabled and integrated into a fast-moving hubbub that, from a distance, seemed to tick along seamlessly. It was as if the city was just waiting for Creative Informatics to come along and now was our time.

My own personal highlights are diverse and plentiful. Being invited to the House of Lords to speak at their Communication and Digital Select Committee's Creative Future Inquiry, and managing to inject a good rant about how awful Brexit has been for our creative industries. Visiting our pop-up exhibition in the National Museum of Scotland and watching the reactions of some of the 32,000 visitors to the new products and services we had supported. The book-shaped cake to celebrate the launch of our book, *Data-Driven Innovation in the Creative Industries*. Plus attending a totally unrelated pottery workshop where I overheard a person I had never met before recommending Creative Informatics and its marvellous work to another artist in the creative community. What we have built is bigger than any individual or institution and its legacy will live on long beyond the project.

So, from its inception, community has been at the very heart of Creative Informatics and I owe this community my thanks. I want to thank Professor Chris Speed, the Founding Director, for inviting me to join him on this journey, and for all that he did for the programme before moving on to pastures new in Australia.

I also want to thank every member of the delivery and programme team, directorate and steering board; we have built something special together. Most of all, I want to thank everyone who took up the opportunities we offered and everyone who took part in Creative Informatics activities. Once we have had the time to have a rest we can look back on this time knowing we came together and achieved something truly wonderful. I hope this report captures some of the scale, scope and ambition of Creative Informatics and documents its legacy as, with excitement, we turn our minds to what this fantastic community will do next.

Professor Melissa Terras,
Director, Creative Informatics
Professor of Digital Cultural Heritage, Design Informatics, Edinburgh College of Art

Founding Director's Report

The Creative Informatics programme spans an extraordinary period for the creative industries in both Edinburgh/regions and across the UK as a whole. Although we co-designed the programme with colleagues and teams across the creative ecosystem in 2017 to address the need for an 'uplift' in data literacy across the sector, little did we imagine that the programme would be so essential.

Not only were the teams ready to provide guidance and support throughout the Covid pandemic with resources (human and digital) that provided essential channels for artists, designers to stay in touch, share stories and learn together, but the programme also foresaw a wave of data-driven technologies that have entirely disrupted the sector.

From introducing unique funding models to encourage experimentation and collaboration with emerging technologies, to providing support, guidance on and inspiration for how best to tackle the ever-evolving systems of AI that continue to reconfigure creative economies and practices, Creative Informatics became a huge community of bright minds that learnt together.

Whilst we set out to deliver 'data-driven innovation for the creative industries', the breadth of inclusion, imagination and insight that the team and community have delivered demonstrates with confidence 'data-driven innovation by the creative industries'. A position of empowerment that we could only have dreamt of.

Although I write from faraway shores, I still sense the glow of a region and community that have embraced data as a material to explore, express and imagine creative futures.

Professor Chris Speed,
Founding Director, Creative Informatics
Professor of Design for Regenerative Futures, Royal Melbourne Institute for Technology (RMIT)

CI IN NUMBERS

130+
R&D PROJECTS

CREATED OR
SAFEGUARDED
445
JOBS

OVERSEEN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF
212
NEW PRODUCTS,
SERVICES OR
EXPERIENCES

45
SPIN-OUTS,
START-UPS
AND PIVOTS

EVERY £1 FUNDING
WE HAVE INVESTED,
HAS LED TO AN IMPACT
OF £18.70
ON THE LOCAL ECONOMY GVA

£7.62M
FURTHER FUNDING
AND INVESTMENT

TRAINED
682
INDIVIDUALS

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion

Diversity is a core value for Creative Informatics and across our programme we have seen 48% female participation (40% male, 12% other/prefer not to say) and 13% global majority participation (against the region's 8.3% population). Recent Inclusive Capital work, in partnership with the Creative Community Hubs project, working in partnership with the Creative Community Hubs project based at WHALE Arts in Wester Hailes, has provided over £157k funding supporting 12 organisations and communities including Euan's Guide, Collective Text, North Edinburgh Arts, Craigmillar Now, and Lung Ha Theatre, to invest in new infrastructure for creative data-driven work with specific equality, diversity and inclusion benefits.

ETHNICITY

GENDER

AGE RANGE

ECONOMIC IMPACT ANALYSIS

FUNDING AND INVESTMENT

Gross Value Added (GVA)

Estimated GVA by the Creative Informatics programme is **£78.5m by 2026**

In June 2024, an economic analysis of the gross economic impact of the Creative Informatics programme was undertaken at the end of its funded period. This independent analysis (undertaken by an economist commissioned by the Data-Driven Innovation programme of the Edinburgh and South-East Scotland City Region Deal) demonstrates that a total of £33.1 million Gross Value Added (GVA) to the Scottish economy is associated with the programme to date, based on current estimates of job levels generated or safeguarded by the programme over 2019/20 to 2022/23, and accounting for subsequent programme participants' business inactivity rates.

Looking ahead, if the 2022/23 participant job levels were to be maintained (i.e., assuming an even balance between some participant's organisations experiencing job growth while others may become inactive) then over the next three years a further £45.5 million GVA (in current price terms) might be generated.

Combining the two estimates above suggests a gross total of £78.5M GVA might be associated with the programme by 2025/26.

For these calculations, GVA per head (across 2018–21) is estimated at £33,253 for new and safeguarded jobs. This is calculated based on relevant industry averages across relevant creative subsectors in the region.

Total support for Creative Informatics across all funders **£8,930,870.74**

Total R&D investment in SMEs by Creative Informatics **£4,197,795.87**

Follow on funding and support achieved by Creative Informatics companies **£7,622,079**

Total additional funding attracted for research and projects related to Creative Informatics **£17,644,745**

Funding allocated to support Edinburgh's Creative Community

Training **£242,644.97**

Dissemination, delivery and capture of events, including hybrid events **£83,732.52**

Hosting and supporting events through local creative organisations **£74,772.32**

Sponsorship and industry support **£88,276.73**

Contracted work and speaker fees for creative freelancers **£201,280.23**

CREATIVE INFORMATICS PARTNERS

Creative Informatics, as an AHRC funded Creative Cluster (2018–2024), was established with the ambition to grow the creative industries in Edinburgh and its regions, and to make the city a world-class centre for creative talent, able to lead data-driven innovation in the creative industries.

Our location was central to our success: Edinburgh is the world's leading festival city, with a range of major annual festivals bringing talent from more than a third of the world's countries to our streets and stages in world-leading celebrations of creativity. Edinburgh is also home to a range of leading cultural and creative institutions – including theatres, libraries, galleries and museums – and cultural experiences, giving it the highest cultural employment levels in the UK. Edinburgh is also one of the UK's largest technology hubs, with a close-knit entrepreneurial community, creating a supportive, collaborative innovation environment, which has been supported by a City Region Deal prioritising data-driven innovation. As a result, international excellence in art, culture and science have become a permanent and inescapable part of Edinburgh's identity. The City and its regions are now a hotbed of cultural interaction, creative innovation and challenging academic thought.

It is against this backdrop that the Creative Informatics programme was delivered, with an aim to grow the creative industries by building the number of existing businesses and creative entrepreneurs who can confidently innovate with data, enabling creatives rather than just the IT/software community to be in the driving seat of data-driven innovation. To do so, Creative Informatics founded a partnership across four organisations: [the University of Edinburgh](#), [Edinburgh Napier University](#), [Codebase](#) and [Creative Edinburgh](#). Each organisation brought a distinct set of skills and experience to the project, and working in such close collaboration has been transformational for the partners and the programme participants alike.

THE UNIVERSITY
of EDINBURGH

Edinburgh Napier
UNIVERSITY

CODEBASE

Creative Edinburgh

Partner: University of Edinburgh

The University of Edinburgh was uniquely placed to host the Creative Informatics cluster, being a world-leading, research-intensive institution with strong links across the city to cultural and technology industry partners. It supports an animated, interdisciplinary cultural scene, with a variety of research projects and public-facing events covering a range of subjects from art, science, film and media to literature, music, technology and more. The University operates at the heart of the cultural and creative scene in Edinburgh and its regions, working year-round in many ways; for example through partnering with the Edinburgh International Festival, the Edinburgh Science Festival, the Edinburgh International Book Festival and others, and providing a home to over one third of Edinburgh Fringe performances.

Creative Informatics was based in Edinburgh College of Art (ECA), an interdisciplinary, modern art school providing higher education in art and design, architecture, history of art and music disciplines for over three thousand students. ECA is at the forefront of research and research-led teaching in the creative arts, humanities and creative technologies, via the Institute for Design Informatics (IDI), which designs systems for better human data interaction, in diverse settings such as health, culture, mobility and finance.

IDI explores design from, with, and by data; the central concern is the design of flows of data which sustain and enhance human values. Relevant technologies include the internet of things, blockchains, robotics, speech recognition, data visualisation, interaction design and social computing, providing a valuable range and source of expertise that Creative Informatics could draw upon.

Creative Informatics also worked with colleagues from the University of Edinburgh's School of Informatics, which for more than five decades has been a global leader in the computational sciences and AI. The School of Informatics is the strongest of its kind in the UK, producing world-leading research and supporting and interacting with a range of innovation and business support measures for the local and global economy. We also drew upon creative industries expertise from the University of Edinburgh's world-leading Business, and Law, Schools.

The IDI was the home of the Creative Informatics delivery team; the range of professional service colleagues who actively delivered and grew the programme, across engagement, communications, finance and evaluation. Design Informatics also hosted a range of Postgraduate Research Associates, supporting Creative Informatics programmes and

designing and documenting our various activities. The unique Design Informatics' events and exhibition space, Inspace, hosted a variety of in-person, hybrid and online events for the programme throughout its five-year duration.

Working together, and with our various partners, the University of Edinburgh team helped those in our creative community looking for funding and support to formulate and articulate ideas, as well as building and testing innovations in different contexts. Our integrated research approaches, using a variety of methods and embedded in artistic and cultural practice, allowed us to conduct research on the current and evolving landscapes of the creative sector in and around Edinburgh, producing over 100 research outputs over the lifetime of the grant

Documentation of the programme, its activities and challenges also led us to come up with a range of policies and protocols, for example in data ethics and data management, which we published openly to model best practice, and these have proven useful to a variety of external organisations. We were proud to be awarded the inaugural Responsible Research Award at the University of Edinburgh's Good Research Practice Awards 2022, for our transparent approach to project management and documentation.

The legacy of the Creative Informatics programme at the University of Edinburgh has been to establish Design Informatics as a leading interdisciplinary hub at the intersection of creativity and technology, leading to further grant-supported activities to support innovation in film, tv, and games, and spawning a range of related research projects. The University team were proud to win the Highly Commended award for Data Transformation of the Year in the 2024 British Data Awards.

Partner: Edinburgh Napier University

Edinburgh Napier University has a tradition of applied practice that contributed to the Creative Informatics project through a human-centred approach to the challenge of engaging with creative practice. This was evidenced through a significant contribution to the Lab and Studio events over the project's lifetime. The main legacies of Creative Informatics were the creation of a new lab infrastructure and the development of an emergent interdisciplinary research culture at Edinburgh Napier University.

This Lab and Studio programme was a key part of the project's engagement with the creative community. The Edinburgh Napier team played a key role in the programming of these events, which were designed to be wide-reaching and have low barriers to participation. This work provided an important first point of contact between Creative Informatics and creative practitioners in the region. For example, it was at a Lab event that an initial meeting took place that resulted in a funded collaboration with Applied Arts Scotland and British Council supported projects in Nepal. The importance of maintaining this community was vital over the peak period of the Covid pandemic, and the team played an important part in the online Friday Forum events in association with Applied Arts Scotland.

The theme of better understanding the needs and priorities of creative practice in relation to data also cut across the Horizon Projects, which formed another strand of Creative Informatics. This was most evident in Horizon 4, which explicitly challenged practitioners to respond to the question of how data impacts on the lived experience and the identity of being a creative practitioner. This work complemented the more explicitly speculative approach of Horizon 3 and the policy focus of Horizon 5. In a similar vein, the Coast to Coast project was a collaboration between Creative Informatics and Future Screens NI that undertook a visual and textual study of creative practice, focusing on individual practitioners in Scotland and Northern Ireland across a range of disciplines.

From the perspective of Edinburgh Napier University, the project enabled us to create the E11 Studio on the Merchiston Campus, which acted as tangible evidence of the project and its impact on infrastructure. At a more pragmatic level, the Small Research Grants were impactful across the university and contributed to a nascent research culture that continues to cut across the disciplinary silos that characterise university culture.

The legacy of the Creative Informatics project for us has been firstly, to build tangible action-based links between colleagues across academic disciplines and secondly, to reinforce the university's position within creative ecology at both a regional and national level.

One of the main contributions of the team at Edinburgh Napier to the Creative Informatics project was their experience in the field of Interaction Design, with its focus on everyday life as experienced through digital artefacts. Central to this is a human-centred approach that seeks to develop understanding that is grounded in people's lived experience. This approach shaped how the team engaged with the creative community over the lifetime of the project and was supplemented by a team member who was both a researcher and a creative practitioner and, critically, part of the wider creative community in the region. Throughout Creative Informatics the goal of the Edinburgh Napier team was to provide opportunities for creative practitioners to articulate their motivations and priorities and how these might be best served by data-driven innovation and technology.

napier.ac.uk

Partner: Codebase

CodeBase is an ecosystem builder that started in Edinburgh in 2014. We are on a mission to grow and strengthen the startup ecosystem in Scotland and the UK, and to show non-technical founders that they have what it takes to launch a successful startup. So we were delighted to have the chance to run Creative Bridge in partnership with Creative Informatics from 2019–2022 and to expand the support we offer founders.

Creative Bridge was a cohort-based pre-accelerator programme designed for creative practitioners in Edinburgh and South-East Scotland. In particular, we wanted to work with founders and potential founders who were interested in moving from a service-led to a product-led business model, and in exploring new approaches to innovation and iteration. Through our work in the tech sector, we had seen hundreds of startups hire people with tech and sales experience but we felt there was a lack of creative talent in the ecosystem and we wanted to change this.

Based around ten weekly sessions, we focused on introducing participants to the building blocks of developing an early-stage tech product; namely, understanding problems, markets and customers before moving on to the build-measure-learn cycle, funding and pitching. As well as this fundamental methodology, demystifying the language around startups and the tech ecosystem was a big component of the programme.

Pre Covid, sessions were run in person at our Edinburgh hub, and welcoming participants into the wider CodeBase community – for example, through free hotdesking, invites to events and founder introductions – was a core part of the offering. From March 2020 to September 2021, during the pandemic, we ran four cohorts of Creative Bridge online only, and through this experience we learnt a lot about how to create an enriching online experience for participants. The last two cohorts in 2022 were run as hybrid events, so participants could attend in person or online, and this flexibility has become central to our courses since Creative Bridge ended that year.

The 220 founders that we supported through the course came from a range of creative sectors, including Architecture (Looper), performing arts (Centrline), fashion and design (Mude), photography (20 Photos) and VR games (BearHammer). At the centre of Creative Bridge was a strong emphasis on community, connecting participants with founders across CodeBase and Creative Informatics, and laying the foundations of effective peer-to-peer support that could continue beyond the end of the cohort.

Working on Creative Bridge has gone on to inform much of our future programme delivery, including a £42m contract with the Scottish Government to run Techscaler, which aims to grow the tech ecosystem across Scotland. We have also worked on a number of new creative industries-focused programmes, including XR Accelerator with XR Network+, and are a partner in the CoSTAR network. This work would not be possible without the foundational work we undertook with the Creative Informatics team on Creative Bridge.

techscaler.co.uk
thisiscodebase.com

Partner: Creative Edinburgh

Creative Edinburgh has been a core partner on the Creative Informatics project since its inception. As a forward thinking and innovative organisation, Creative Edinburgh seeks to unite creative thinkers across the city through events, career support and advocacy. It brings together and supports Edinburgh's creative community by providing a space for creation, collaboration and connection for creative professionals throughout their career. At the heart of things is the ambition to protect the welfare of the creative community through services for creative freelancers, sole traders and startups that allow them to develop and thrive, supporting creative careers, collaboration and encouraging innovation across the creative industries in Edinburgh, Scotland and beyond.

Creative Edinburgh delivered the Connected Innovators programme, providing an opportunity for emerging leaders in the creative industries to apply for funding for research and development or professional development around data and data-driven innovation. The recipients of this programme have done incredible work in their communities by leading their own independent research projects. Whilst their projects all have the same theme around data innovation, the 27 projects supported by the funding from Creative Informatics are extremely varied, exciting and impactful.

In addition to delivering the Connected Innovators programme, we also supplied mentoring for recipients of the Resident Entrepreneur programme.

creative-edinburgh.com

PROGRAMMES AND PROJECTS

From 2018–2024, Creative Informatics offered a variety of funding opportunities for individuals and organisations to create inspiring work with data. Funding programmes were designed to provide support across a variety of levels and experience, meeting the needs of those working across the creative industries in Edinburgh and South-East Scotland.

Programme: Resident Entrepreneur

The Resident Entrepreneur programme supported individuals or small teams with ambitions to develop a new product or service using data or data-driven technology, with funding of up to £12,000 available to support this work. Eight funding rounds supported 74 participants or groups to develop their data-driven ideas in response to one of the following R&D priorities:

- ◇ Developing access to and engagement with new audiences and markets.
- ◇ Developing new modalities of experience.
- ◇ Unlocking the value of archives and datasets.
- ◇ Exploring new business models for the creative industries.

Successful applicants received grant funding plus mentorship and support to bring their ideas to life, and Resident Entrepreneur projects have covered the breadth of the creative industries. Innovations include the development of playful tech like Playable Technology's *BeatBlocks* – an app that allows users to make music with everyday building blocks – and Bearhammer Games' innovative *Venture's Gauntlet*, a challenging VR obstacle course full of adventure and puzzles set amongst beautiful and dramatic views of the Scottish Highlands.

The programme also supported those looking to experiment with sustainable ways of working and/or themes. Knitwear designer Jeni Allison's *Custom Loop* was designed to tackle wastage and excess in fashion manufacturing by allowing users to order custom-made designer items, whilst Rebecca Kaye's *Ploterre* uses principles from the fields of mathematics and design to create striking artwork from environmental data.

The final Resident Entrepreneur call closed in September 2022 and across the life of the project 74 Resident Entrepreneurs developed 42 new Minimum Viable Products (MVPs); 89 new products, services or experiences; 21 spin-outs or start-ups and secured a total of 106 new or safeguarded jobs, with total follow-on funding of more than £7 million.

Fully funded by DDI, it supported 74 SMEs to undertake R&D with data, receiving £12k funding, mentorship through Creative Edinburgh and expert support from the Creative Informatics team. We were the first funder of Touchlab, an electronic skin startup who went on to secure £3.5m funding from Octopus Ventures. Other supported Entrepreneurs include: Jeni Allison whose *Custom Loop* enables a radical rethink of knitwear production enabling scalable bespoke pieces; and DataMind Audio, who launched *The Combobulator* in early 2024, an ethical AI plugin for music production using neural nets of "artists brains" and creating a revenue stream back to artists.

Resident Entrepreneur Case Study Touchlab

Like being there: How Touchlab use robot avatars with the revolutionary ability to touch to facilitate remote healthcare

Programmes: Resident Entrepreneur and Creative Bridge
Funding: £12,000 plus mentoring and support
Sector: Robotics, healthcare, tech innovation
Themes: Robotics

Founded in 2018 by Dr Zaki Hussein, Touchlab is a start up with a young and vibrant culture, based at The Higgs Centre for Innovation in Edinburgh. The company is focused on building and developing the future of sensing technology and/or electronic skin (e-skin) to enable machines to possess the sense of touch. Rather than just supplying an e-skin, Touchlab design systems to integrate the sensing technology into any surface, and additionally develop the software and visualisers around it.

This e-skin, which is thinner than human skin, is effectively wrapped around a robot to allow it to touch. Machines fitted with e-skin can roll pens, grasp soft objects and detect slip, even in extreme conditions – such as acid, high- and low-temperatures and radioactive environments – opening up huge potential for its use, including in space exploration.

In 2020, Touchlab applied to be a Creative Informatics Resident Entrepreneur, looking to add expertise in software AR and VR integration into the team's skill set to design an intuitive 3D/AR interface and further the development of a teleoperated avatar system, Nexi, which would be able to gather huge quantities of sensory data. This avatar system, which comprises a robot, VR and AR systems and Touchlab's hallmark e-skin in a single operator-controlled system, will essentially allow an operator to see, hear, speak and feel through a robot, regardless of their location (within 400km). This in turn would allow specialist and high-quality care to be dispensed more easily and allow healthcare providers to spend less time fulfilling basic operations, therefore reducing the strain on healthcare systems.

Though the existing team had already started building the robotic system and integrating the first sensors, work was still needed to translate this data to a controller. Bringing the systems together via this additional expertise would increase the quality and effectiveness of their equipment demonstrations, an essential sales tool for technology of this nature.

Touchlab aimed to achieve the aims of this project in a creative way, for instance, using synesthesia. For example, a medical avatar evaluating a patient's fever could translate heat on the fingertips to the controller, see the temperature rise on the headset, or even smell the high temperature as a scent. To manage this, both an experienced software developer and 3D graphics programming developer would be required.

The output of this work was entered into the 2021 ANA XPrize Avatar competition (<https://www.xprize.org/prizes/avatar/finalist-teams>), a four-year global competition, offering a prize purse of \$10M, focused on the development of an avatar system that will deploy a human's senses, actions and presence to a remote location in real time, leading to a more connected world. Of the 77 qualified teams, 38 were selected as semi-finalists and 15 as finalists, of which Touchlab were one, presenting their work at an event in Miami, Florida.

Though finding new talent with the highly specialised and in-demand skills needed proved to be a challenge, particularly in the face of Covid and Brexit immigration restrictions, Touchlab managed to on-board two new team members (one part-time, and the other full-time). These new team members had the knowledge and experience needed to translate data from the robot Avatar to a controller VR headset, force-feedback gloves and force-feedback suit. The funding also allowed the wider team to dedicate more time to upskilling and developing their knowledge of creating virtual environments.

Equipment purchased with Creative Informatics' Resident Entrepreneur funding enabled the acquisition of a Robotiq gripper, which was mounted to the Avatar to facilitate delicate grasping and make possible tasks such as plugging a charger into a socket. A VR headset pack was also purchased, and the company was able to finance a force-feedback suit (Teslasuit), all of which enhanced the feeling of immersion into the virtual reality world for the Avatar operator. As with many other Resident Entrepreneurs,

the mentorship provided by the programme was particularly praised by Touchlab for helping team members to find their voice and develop ways of effectively communicating across the team and beyond.

Touchlab has received significant co-investment from Scottish Edge (£100,000), Scottish Enterprise (£25,500), and TechStart Ventures Scotland (£600,000). In early 2022, they received a £3.5million investment from Octopus Ventures, one of Europe's largest and most active early-stage investors, to expand and accelerate their work by strengthening their commercial and tech teams to better meet the increasing demand for its visionary product and its myriad potential uses. In 2023, they were ranked 41 in *Startups' 100 Index* (<https://startups.co.uk/startups-100/2023/touchlab/>).

In early 2023, Touchlab began a real-world pilot of their technology within a hospital environment, deploying its robot and e-skin technology within a geriatric acute ward in Finland. Though currently focused on medical deployments of the equipment, Touchlab believes that the creative industries could benefit from their technology across a range of scenarios, including providing more inclusive and interactive ways of experiencing museum collections and stage shows, particularly for those with access or sensory needs, or who may not be able to travel easily outside of their living environment, transforming live video performances into full sensory experiences. There can be no doubt that we are at the very beginning of the exploration, development and implementation of tactile technology, and that its transformative impact on a wide range of areas will only become more apparent as further products are developed and pilots are tested across environments and scenarios. All signs are that Touchlab will continue to be at the forefront of these exciting developments.

<https://www.touchlab.io/>

Programme: Connected Innovators

The Connected Innovators programme was created to support emerging leaders from within the creative industries who wanted to take time out to experiment and undertake some research and development to further their business and/or career. Professionals looking to develop a specific area of creative practice or business using data or data-driven technology could apply for funding to support this work through:

- ◇ New approaches, for example, problem solving, income-generation, developing new skills, identifying new collaborations or learning to work with new tools or technologies.
- ◇ Scaling-up, including engaging with new markets, expanding staff expertise and teams or developing new products or services at scale.
- ◇ Supporting communities by showcasing or facilitating work happening within the community, collective or studio.

Led by Creative Informatics partner Creative Edinburgh, Connected Innovators provided 27 creatives with £10k funding, mentoring and additional support and advice to undertake R&D to develop or pivot their practice. Participants included: Mella Shaw, whose resultant ceramics and data sonification work on sonar pollution, *Sounding Line*, won the British Ceramics Biennial Award 2023; Andrew Brooks, whose data driven exhibition on Functional Neurological Disorders, *FND Stories*, won the Art of Neuroscience 2023; and Ana Betancourt of Black Goblin Audio, who won the Trickstar Business Award for innovation in animation at the Stuttgart Festival of Animated Film 2024.

In total the programme supported 27 SMEs or individuals across four funded cohorts, with successful applicants receiving facilitated peer support and funding of up to £10,000. Connected Innovators created five new MVPs, 34 new products and 14 new services or experiences.

Connected Innovator Case Study Mella Shaw

From the shoreline back to the sea: How ceramicist Mella Shaw created award-winning visual art from cetacean stranding data.

Programme: Connected Innovators

Funding: £12,958 + mentoring

BCS Award Prize: £10,000

Sector: Visual art

Themes: Ceramics, cetaceans, strandings, environment, art exhibition, visual art

Mella Shaw is an artist who uses the medium of clay to make consciousness-raising work about environmental issues. In 2019 she heard about the increased number of mass strandings of cetaceans along the West Coast of Scotland and the large amount of data gathered by the Scottish Marine Animal Stranding Scheme (SMASS) around these tragic and increasingly common events. It is now understood (by leading scientists such as Dr Andrew Kitchener and Georg Hanke at the National Museum of Scotland) that the beachings have a direct link to mid-water-sonar used in naval exercises and oil exploration in the affected areas. This has a devastating effect on marine life, in particular, on the deepest diving species of whales (such as bottlenose and Cuvier's beaked whales) that depend on echolocation.

Mella's craft-based artistic practice focuses on highlighting environmental issues and allowing the public access to statistics or scientific data in engaging ways, and she wanted to tell the story of these whales and how deadly this mid-water sonar – an invisible pollutant – is to these protected species. Mella's Connected Innovators project allowed her to undertake a period of research and development to further her work on the project, which was subsequently titled *Sounding Line*, with the specific intention of travelling to the Hebrides to collect a sample of whale bones to make a completely new type of clay; whale-bone-china.

With permission from Nature Scotland, Mella created her own whale-bone-china to make an installation of large-scale forms inspired by the shape of a whale's tiny inner-ear bones. This work represented a new area of practice for Mella, exploring innovative ways to combine and incorporate the stranding data that is so key to this subject. Consideration was given not only to using statistics on the types and locations of the strandings, but also to exploring how the sonar itself could be represented to communicate an understanding of the animals, their behaviour and how it is disrupted. To this end, Mella collaborated with Theodore Koterwas, a digital artist with expertise in sound. Together, they developed a system delivering a pulse vibration based on mid-water-sonar, which was passed through large red ropes wrapped around and suspending the ceramic forms, harmoniously uniting these two elements of the project and creating an immersive sensory work.

Sustainability is a key element of all Mella's work, and in order to reduce its environmental impact she initially hoped not to have to fire the work created. However, the sculptures were too vulnerable to withstand the vibration in the rope if unfired. Serendipitously, this initial idea of leaving the work unfired inspired Mella to travel back to the Outer Hebrides in summer 2023 in order to return one of the forms to the sea, capturing this process on film (funded by Creative Informatics Project Extension Funding), which was then incorporated into the final exhibition to further tell the story of the cetaceans; their provenance, where they had died, and their restoration to the ocean which had been their home.

In October 2023, *Sounding Line* was one of ten exhibits, by artists considered to be making innovative work in the field of contemporary ceramics, selected to be in the AWARD exhibition of the *British Ceramics Biennial* in Stoke-on-Trent, and was eventually announced as the overall winner of the £10,000 prize. This huge achievement, with an important environmental message, has brought Mella's work to a broad new audience. *Sounding Line* was also shown in February 2024 at Summerhall in Edinburgh and, at the time of writing, further opportunities for exhibiting around the country are being explored.

Presenting the award, Alun Graves, Chair of the Award selection panel and the V&A's Senior Curator, Ceramics and Glass 1900–now, commented:

“Mella Shaw's *Sounding Line* is a truly exceptional and remarkable work, powerful in concept and majestic in execution. It represents in every aspect an extraordinary feat of making, rendering a work that is both poetic and sublimely beautiful, but also confronting and unequivocal in its message. Mella Shaw has realised a work of huge ambition, demonstrating the potency of ceramics and its ability to engage with the issues of our time.”

“When making my original application I was clear that one of the reasons to apply was that Creative Edinburgh through Connected Innovators would give me an opportunity to meet other people with the necessary skill set and knowledge to push the data/interactive element of the project forward. I feel very lucky to have been introduced to Theodore Koterwas at the Innovation Showcase 2022. It would not have been possible for me to have made this work in the form it is without his input.”

Mella Shaw
<https://www.mellashaw.co.uk/>

Programme: Challenge Projects

Challenge Projects offered an opportunity for creative and cultural organisations to bring forward challenges relating to their work that require innovative, data-driven solutions.

These “Challenge Holders” brought unformed or semi-formed challenges that were co-designed with the Creative Informatics team, with up to £20,000 available to support Challenge Respondents (individuals or SMEs) whose proposals were matched to the relevant Challenge Holder.

Proposals were invited to respond to one of the following priorities:

- ◇ Developing access to and engagement with new audiences and markets.
- ◇ Developing new modalities of experience.
- ◇ Unlocking the value of archives and datasets.
- ◇ Exploring new business models for the creative industries.

These challenges and subsequent collaborations created some interesting projects (such as)

Creative Informatics created seven rounds of Challenge applications and supported 29 participants or SMEs to develop data-driven solutions to the challenges set. Through the 29 Challenge Projects, 18 new Minimum Viable Products (MVPs), 41 new products, services or experiences and 3 new spin-outs or start-ups were created. In addition, 36 jobs were safeguarded, 14 new jobs created, and the projects attracted follow-on funding of close to £1M.

29 Challenge projects brought organisations including Historic Environment Scotland, Edinburgh Festival Fringe, National Theatre of Scotland, Traverse, New Media Scotland, The List and Vintage Vibes together with SMEs who undertook R&D projects – funded with £20k and further support and advice from Creative Informatics – resulting in innovative solutions and ongoing collaborations and raising awareness of data-driven innovation amongst the teams in larger cultural organisations.

Challenge Projects Case Study Ray Interactive

Using technology to build on Scottish historical records and engage visitors with Scottish ancestors and connections.

Programmes: Resident Entrepreneur, Challenge Projects, Creative Bridge

Funding: £97,000

Sector: Events, Heritage, Cultural

Themes: Interactivity, music, audio, tech, public events, engagement, accessibility

Ray Interactive are a creative technology company, co-founded by Brendan McCarthy and Sam Healy, who have participated in Creative Informatics in several strands including Creative Bridge and Resident Entrepreneurs, as well as being selected as a Responder for the St Giles Challenge (in Round 5, 2021).

St Giles' Cathedral was founded in 1124 by King David I and has been a working church for almost 900 years. Based on the High Street – part of Edinburgh's busy Royal Mile – it is one of the ten most visited buildings in Scotland, receiving more than a million visitors every year, of whom 80% are from outside of the UK. For their challenge they wanted to find an interactive and visually appealing way to connect with the Scottish diaspora, building on Scottish historical records.

Ray Interactive worked closely with St Giles to develop a thoughtful physical installation and digital platform that will help visitors engage with Scottish ancestors and connections and extend their experience through further exploration. Whilst there were some challenging delays in securing the data, the partnership between Ray Interactive and St Giles remained strong, with shared learnings and exploration taking place throughout. The solution developed will launch later, but there have already been benefits to both parties.

St Giles have found the process transformational, hugely benefitting from their work with Brendan and Sam, but also embracing this opportunity to engage in creative R&D as a highly engaged Challenge Holder and using their learnings to kick-start a whole new stream of digital work, saying:

“It would be hard to summarise how my understanding of tech has improved. As part of the networking due to Creative Informatics, we have created a video game in collaboration with the University of Glasgow, we are looking at implementing robots and also AI... Being a part of Creative Informatics was the beginning of our tech journey.”

Also noting that their experience as a Challenge Holder with Ray Interactive, and their engagement with the wider Creative Informatics programme, as having...

“opened my eyes to the talent and network of creatives in Scotland who are ready to implement innovative digital solutions to problems”.

vimeo.com/574076560

For Ray Interactive the challenge was an opportunity to dig into complex historical datasets and explore how to bring semi-familiar genealogical data to life in a new and compelling way, appropriate to the Medieval setting but adopting modern technologies and opportunities for data exploration. Working with St Giles has presented unique data and communications challenges but has also opened Ray Interactive's work to a whole new set of potential clients and audiences in the tourism space.

Inclusive Capital Funding Calls

Creative Informatics was awarded additional funding by the Arts & Humanities Research Council (part of UK Research & Innovation) in 2023 to support investment in capital projects (like buildings, facilities, technology, equipment, software and maintenance), which supported the legacy of projects and helped further the equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI) impact of creative data-driven innovation in our region.

In Spring 2023, we shared a number of funding calls for inclusive projects aimed at making a real difference to diverse communities and to enabling new and more inclusive opportunities for creative innovation in Edinburgh and South-East Scotland. These included:

- ◇ Creative Informatics Participant & Alumni Creative Tech Fund.
- ◇ Community Creative Tech Fund, in partnership with Creative Community Hubs.
- ◇ Creative Informatics Inclusive Innovation Working Spaces Fund – supporting professional accommodation for creative tech and data-driven startups and SMEs in Edinburgh and South-East Scotland.

Applicants were encouraged to read more about our approach to EDI in our policy and action plan, which has informed all of our work, and to ensure their application responded to our robust approach

to facilitating equality and diversity within the community. The funding also provided investment in equipment, enabling work with diverse communities (including support for Creative Edinburgh's work with diverse creative communities), and acquisition of a body scanner, housed at the University of Edinburgh, which can be used in inclusive and innovative academic fashion/body tech research as well as in industry collaborations and R&D.

- ◇ The Community Creative Tech Fund was designed and run in close partnership with the Creative Community Hubs project, a network supporting creative community hubs in Edinburgh that are based in and responsive to diverse, underserved communities. The fund was open only to organisations with a clear EDI impact, and a total of £157k of awards were made to 12 organisations in the region.
- ◇ The Participant and Alumni Creative Tech Fund invited members of the Creative Informatics community who had previously received funding or support to submit EDI-focused capital investments for funding consideration, with a total of ten awards made.
- ◇ The Inclusive Innovation Working Spaces Fund has secured working spaces across the region for creatives working on EDI-focused projects, or who themselves are from diverse and underrepresented backgrounds; these were allocated through a rolling open call.

Community Creative Tech Fund Case Study

Lung Ha Theatre Company

How data-driven tools and technologies are supporting Lung Ha Theatre Company to shape a more equitable future for learning-disabled artists.

Programme: Community Creative Tech Fund

Funding: £8,623

Sector: Performing arts

Themes: EDI, theatre, performance, disability

Scotland's leading theatre company for people with learning disabilities, Lung Ha Theatre Company (LHTC) works across Scotland, the UK and internationally, "proudly making fabulous theatre" by and with individuals with learning disabilities.

Since 1984, the company has worked with over 400 actors, created over 50 original productions and worked with many leading artists and organisations from across Scotland's creative industries to produce original theatre productions. Currently, the company works with an ensemble of 26 learning-disabled actors who attend weekly sessions to develop their creative skills, devise new productions and engage in training, learning and creative development. In addition to a small core staff team, a wider group of volunteer supporters, consisting of parents, carers and other support networks help to deliver activities.

Lung Ha applied for £8,623 of investment to expand their IT and technology infrastructure and equipment, support a sustainable and strategic vision for their activities and achieve significant impacts for staff, beneficiaries and volunteers, benefitting everyone connected to the company and their audiences. Specifically, funding was to be distributed amongst new CRM software, items of hardware (including laptops, phones and a projector for community screenings and recorded performances), hiring of an accessible rehearsing space and a range of access provisions to support their performers, including text-to-speech software that allows learning-disabled members of Lung Ha's community to contribute fully to the company's activities.

Investment in accessible rehearsal space has directly empowered the organisation to advance its social and artistic aims, expanding their work across Scotland with the development of Lung Ha Across Scotland, a new touring initiative for learning-disabled actors that will launch in 2024. As part of this initiative, Lung Ha will develop a pathway for learning-disabled adults to engage professionally, as paid artists in the creative sector, through new training and professional opportunities.

Investment in new hardware has supported access provisions for approximately 37 learning-disabled adults across the company's work (LHTC Touring Company, LHTC Ensemble, LH Across Scotland and other creative development projects). Whilst the software and equipment purchased can respond to disability and/or social access barriers and provide proactive provisions to meet requirements and ensure that everyone has fair access to ways of improving how they work. Unexpectedly, this has also allowed Lung Ha to make investments in their fair work action plan, ahead of schedule, and ensure that equality across staff conditions is embedded.

Acquisition of an improved CRM system has significantly increased Lung Ha's audience engagement, allowing them to achieve further investment through an individual giving and donation pathway. This is key to supporting LHTC during their 40th anniversary year and their aims to increase audience engagement and financial donation turnover and build towards an exciting programme of work, for which the Touring Company sits proudly at the centre.

As Lung Ha Theatre Company marks its 40th anniversary in 2024, the Community Creative Tech Fund has allowed them to evolve their offering and presented an exciting opportunity to introduce new beneficiaries and audiences around Scotland to the joy of their work, and what can be achieved by members of their community for many more years to come.

"This funding has enabled us to take tangible steps towards [exploring] what steps can be taken towards equitable and fair pay for learning-disabled artists in receipt of state support."

Arron Greechan, Lung Ha Theatre Company

<https://www.lungha.com/>

Creative AI DEMONSTRATOR

An additional Creative AI strand undertook research with the creative sector across Scotland to understand their engagement, needs, concerns and barriers to engaging with AI. The project also supported ten small-scale music and audio R&D pilots across Scotland, with resultant work including improved music/gameplay synching for VR adventure fitness games from Bearhammer Games, a collaborative art-making and music-generation experience powered by explainable AI from Aberdeen-based Painting Music, and live music and a new audio artwork by Scott Myles and Oscar Prentice-Middleton to be shown at Glasgow Gallery of Modern Art from July 2024–February 2025. An openly licensed paper sharing the findings of this programme was published in May 2024, with a closing showcase held in partnership with the Scottish AI Alliance in Glasgow in June 2024 as a starting point for ongoing dialogue across the sector.

Creative AI Case Study DataMind Audio

Breaking new ground with ethically sourced audio AI: Ben Cantill's DataMind Audio and the development of the Combobulator.

Programmes: Resident Entrepreneur, Creative AI Music & Audio Pilot Project

Funding: £12,000 + £5,000

Sector: Music and audio

Themes: Artist development, freelance, fair-pay, music and audio innovation, events, festivals

DataMind Audio is a pioneering company that operates at the intersection of music and AI. Created by musicians for musicians – and led by electronic music producer, educator, entrepreneur and technologist, Ben Cantill (Encanti) – their mission is to produce innovative electronic instruments that leverage the power of AI to expand and augment human creativity and capability in the realm of sound design.

In 2022, DataMind were accepted on to the final round of the Creative Informatics' Resident Entrepreneur programme, proposing to use the £12,000 grant to support their five-strong core team in developing a groundbreaking new AI plugin, the *Combobulator*.

Using AI-models trained on the audio from world-class music producers (with their explicit permission), the *Combobulator* transforms a live audio signal to sound like the selected music producer's unique style. Whilst this programming of an AI to "hallucinate" an interpretation of an audio signal itself represents a completely new paradigm for creative sound design, the plug-in comes with many modular controls familiar to synthesizer users.

Development of the *Combobulator* enabled DataMind to understand the online marketplace for ethically-sourced neural networks, which will create a new economic opportunity for artists in the AI space. By curating the world's finest collection of neural networks and establishing a global marketplace for AI generative implementations of their work, DataMind Audio is providing a new income stream for music producers to earn royalties, addressing the financial insecurity faced by artists. This represents a significant market innovation, and initial sharing of the product suggests a positive reception by the music software industry.

Furthermore, the idea of a neural network marketplace, where trained networks can be sold based on specific artist datasets, has broader implications beyond sound design. This concept could potentially be applied to other forms of media in various creative industries. As the technology rapidly expands and accelerates, DataMind aim to actively participate in the conversation surrounding its applications in all creative industries.

Participating in the Resident Entrepreneur programme helped the DataMind team develop as researchers, audio specialists, artists and community members. Mentorship was provided by Tinderbox Orchestra's Luci Holland, whose expertise in the UK music industry and astute insights proved to be an invaluable resource and have helped position DataMind for success.

Whilst their primary focus continues to be on further developing the *Combobulator* (in particular enhancing its security measures to ensure the protection of IP, user data and prevent any potential security/piracy risks) the team are also working on the *Refractalizer*, which combines granular synthesis techniques with AI neural audio synthesis. This represents another exciting avenue through which to expand the company's portfolio of cutting-edge audio plugins, and provides a unique tool for music producers to explore innovative sound design possibilities.

In addition to the production of these tools, this project has also deepened the team's awareness and understanding of ethical considerations (e.g., around data privacy and ownership of generated content) in the emerging field of AI creativity and has helped them craft ethical policies for the company's use of artist content for data training.

DataMind are committed to paying royalties of 50% of the sales price of each model, after the initial expense of training the model has been covered. More widely, they hope to become a model company for

generating ethical training data, working with artists in the AI music space to become the UK's premier ethically-sourced AI neural audio software company. In the coming months, they intend to explore further opportunities in funding, marketing, research, and development to achieve these aims.

On 9 November 2022, DataMind Audio Ltd was registered as a limited company, and the *Combobulator* was launched in January 2024. Whilst the instrument is now more dynamic and expressive than initially imagined, and additional features (such as model blending and side-chain functionalities), have been identified, further work on resolving inconsistencies in sound quality and the processing power usage of models is being undertaken before its full unveiling.

Since their participation in Resident Entrepreneurs, the company has been successful in gaining a further £5,000 of R&D funding through Creative Informatics' Creative AI Music & Audio Pilot Project to retrain the *Combobulator* using an improved version of the current algorithm to enable the tool to scale more quickly and efficiently, and reduce the likelihood of it being swamped by larger-scale competitors. They also received funding from Innovate UK to train a number of Model Reliability Engineers, who will specialise in training the tool's neural networks in close collaboration with the artists whose styles they will be applying, and with ethical considerations at the forefront.

"Our experience with Creative Informatics has been invaluable. From the kick-off meeting with other grant winners and the CI team, we were inspired by the collective creativity and innovation within the community. Nicola's advice and support have been instrumental in navigating the Catalyst Grant Application process, and we are grateful to have her as our mentor. It feels like we have a reliable support system in place."
Ben Cantil

<https://datamindaudio.ai/>

Programme: Creative Bridge

Creative Bridge was a ten-week, cohort-based education programme designed to introduce creative practitioners to start-up thinking, innovation and digital product development. It was delivered by CodeBase; the UK's largest, and one of Europe's fastest-growing, technology incubators, (<https://thisiscodebase.com/>), as one of the six Creative Informatics activity strands.

Since 2019, ten cohorts and a total of 220 individuals completed the Creative Bridge programme, which centred around three learning outcomes:

1. Turning a creative idea into a sustainable business.
2. Breaking down barriers into the startup world by demystifying the jargon around tech entrepreneurship.
3. Sharing toolkits and processes that empower creatives to respond to fast change and to cultivate resilience.

Within the Creative Informatics cluster, Creative Bridge was a first step for creatives looking to develop an early-stage idea, with the ambition of taking them from plan to pitch and equipping them with the tools to grow their idea beyond the programme. Through the programme, 122 new MVPs were created alongside seven new products, services or experiences and 20 new spin-outs or startups.

As part of Creative Bridge's legacy, Codebase has gone on to deliver a specially tailored version of the programme, Codebase Bridge, as a 10-credit (SCQF Level 11) course for the Edinburgh Futures Institute. A further Virtual Production Bridge will be developed and delivered by Codebase, via the XR Network+, in 2024, building on the legacy of Creative Bridge and Codebase's collaboration with Creative Informatics.

Creative Bridge Case Study Looper

Using data and AI to solve carbon data knowledge gaps to move toward net zero in architectural design and construction.

Programmes: Creative Bridge
Funding: £17,000

Sector: Architecture and Design

Themes: Sustainability, waste reduction, innovation, construction, industrial development

Looper's co-founder, Yiqiang Zhao participated in Creative Bridge as part of Cohort 5 in 2020 and used the time to research and develop the company's MVP; cloud-based AI-powered 3D modelling software created to accelerate architectural design towards net zero. Upon completion of Creative Bridge, Looper successfully applied to the Resident Entrepreneur programme and focused on developing a prototype carbon calculation tool for use in architectural planning, which they estimate saves up to 85% of the cost and only takes 15% of the analysis time of traditional carbon consultation.

In 2021, Looper was selected for the 2021 Engage, Invest, Exploit (EIE) cohort – an intensive support programme matching potentially high-growth Edinburgh companies with investors – and pitched at the EIE conference. At the same time, the company secured pre-seed funding through the Data-Driven Entrepreneurship programme (supported by the Scottish Funding Council) and was also selected for a place in cohort 3 of the UK High-Speed Rail (HS2) business accelerator programme, competing against 100 other startups for their place. In January 2022, with a proposal to create a scalable Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) solution for goods-producing businesses, Looper won the CivTech Sprint Challenge, focused on how technology can support the South of Scotland's circular economy and net zero ambitions.

Looper's work demonstrates the crucial contribution creative sector companies – in this case a tech-enabled architectural design innovation company – make to the wider industrial innovation landscape, with impact on construction and energy, and beneficial environmental and social impacts through more carbon neutral architectural design coming to fruition. As a team with international backgrounds who have chosen to base their business in Edinburgh, Looper also reflects the invaluable contribution the diverse community living and working in Edinburgh makes to the creative sector.
<https://www.looper.design/>

CREATIVE INFORMATICS USE OF FLEXIBLE FUNDS

Creative Informatics was unusually privileged in having flexibility in how best to engage and support the sector through some of our funding, particularly that provided through the Scottish Funding Council. This enabled us to support data-driven innovation and innovative tech practices in the creative industries through a number of additional activities and support routes.

Sponsorship

As part of our outreach we were delighted to sponsor a wide range of activities and events for the sector including: the International Magazine Festival (2019); the Edinburgh Innovations Creative Business Ideas Competition (2019, 2020); the Turing Fest tech conference (2021, as Diversity Supporter); Tinderbox's Playaway Games Festival (2021); British Computing Society (BCS)' Human Computer Interaction event (2022); Creative Tech Scotland Gathering (2022), which we have also supported through hosting, participation and recommendation of speakers and demonstrators; IEE VISAP'22, a mini-conference and exhibition at the intersection of data visualisation, art and design; the *Sounds of Deep Fake* exhibition at the Edinburgh Fringe Festival and Edinburgh Art Festival (2023), which received a 4-star review in *The List* and coverage on BBC Radio 4's *Front Row*; Mella Shaw's *Sounding Line* exhibition (2023-4); the Edinburgh Book Festival (2024); the Edinburgh Science Festival (2024); and the Creative Edinburgh Awards (2020-3). We also facilitated support for a cohort of Scottish participants to attend Music Tech Fest Labs 2022 in Portugal, working with Creative Tech Scotland Gathering and funder Creative Scotland.

We were proud to support Sustainable Fashion Scotland's *Generation of Waste*, an exhibit selected for the Blue Zone (delegate-only area) of COP26 in Glasgow (2021), and which continues to tour and encourage reflection on and engagement in the impact of fashion on climate change. We have also sponsored a strand of design and creative community engagement work as part of the Regenerative Futures Fund's ambitious mission to "create a ten-year, unrestricted pooled fund for the social sector in Edinburgh to work upstream towards big, transformational change for people."

Creative Informatics worked closely with the Marine Alliance for Science and Technology Scotland (MASTS) and partners Blue Action EU project and People Ocean Planet to support Ocean ARTic. Funded by Creative Scotland and commissioned in the year of COP26, the Ocean ARTic partnership brought together creatives and marine climate scientists to explore innovative ways to tell the story of the impact of climate change in the Arctic and Scotland through climate data. Two artists, Eve Mosher and Michael Begg, were commissioned to develop new works. Mosher worked with Creative Informatics participants InChat in the development of her work, *Holding the Ocean: A Journey Connecting Scotland and the Ocean* . Begg's work became a new album and accompanying multimedia performance piece based on arctic climate change data, *Light Water is*

Black Water, which was memorably previewed at the Creative Informatics online lab in November 2021 and premiered in full at the Queen's Hall Edinburgh in 2022. The work was covered by the press, including BBC Radio 3 and BBC Alba, and has led to Michael Begg's continued work with Arctic climate change scientists and he has gone onto being appointed as the first Friends of the Scott Polar Research Institute musician in residence. He was hosted by the Royal Navy aboard the ice patrol vessel, HMS Protector.

Finally, we have been delighted to be able to support projects and community members to extend their work or develop versions of it for new contexts, locations and audiences, so that they can take advantage of emerging opportunities. For example, supporting: Victoria Evans (Small Grants recipient) to adapt her project *Tidesong* (developed with Creative Informatics alumni Ray Interactive) for a commission by the Xunta de Galicia to make work for a survey exhibition on movement in art, in Santiago de Compostela, Spain; a cohort of Creative Informatics companies to participate in the Immersive Futures Lab at SXSW 2023; Pollyanna (Challenge Holder) and Bliind Studios (Challenge Responder) to undertake the first public interactive screening of *Sore Throat* (2023) by Davide Bugarin and Adam Castle at Edinburgh's Fruitmarket Gallery in November 2023.

Training and Development

Creative Informatics provided additional support for Creative Edinburgh's Raise Your Game digital skills programme, funded by the Edinburgh Futures Institute, which ran for the first time as a pilot in Autumn 2020. Raise Your Game supported creatives, typically freelancers and sole traders, to develop their business. We additionally supported a series of funded places on several runs of the course, thus reducing barriers to participation, and supported the Creative Edinburgh online public events series Future Gaze, which looked at emerging technology topics with expert guest speakers.

Creative Informatics worked with Daydream Believers, an organisation curating and disseminating high-quality creative teaching resources which can then be used by teachers in schools and further education (FE) contexts, to create three Creative Informatics resources covering: *Dream Team*, approaches to developing creative teams (2 lessons); *Creative Industries*, an introduction to sectors, roles and skills across the creative industries (2 lessons); and *Designing with Data*, an introduction to designing data-driven services (2 lessons). All are available at: <https://daydreambelievers.co.uk/believers/creative-informatics/>

Edinburgh Innovations (EI) have been a central part of the Creative Informatics team since the outset, and we have worked closely with them to ensure that our companies, projects and community members can access skills and expertise from EI to support the development of their businesses. We have also jointly delivered events and partnered with EI, and wider University of Edinburgh colleagues, on events at University Creative and Cultural Careers weeks. Similarly, we have worked with organisations – including Interface, who were a key part of our initial funding selection panels, and EIE (Engage, Invest, Exploit) – to support the development of supported creatives, including funding a cohort of companies to attend the EIE 2020 international investor showcase, to see the investment pitching process in action and engage with local startups, many working in the tech space.

The Creative Informatics team have also worked with Edinburgh Napier University's careers events and support for businesses throughout the project, including with Bright Red Triangle, Edinburgh Napier University's enterprise hub. More recently (2023–4) we developed and supported a number of events focused on skills for startup founders, which were designed, in part, in response to feedback to founders and companies we had been supporting and their requests for skills support in specific areas.

Whilst Creative Informatics have benefited from the participation of or partnership with brilliant skills organisations, at times the creatives we have been working with have needed specific specialised skills, and we have also supported a number of additional skills initiatives or supported individuals to take part in other relevant courses or opportunities. This included specialist data "train the trainer" sessions for the Creative Informatics team to enable onward support for the creative community, commissioned from local specialists CodeClan and Effini and supported by additional support from the AHRC.

Covid-related initiatives

Creative Informatics had just begun delivery across all programme strands when the Covid pandemic and its associated lockdowns began. In addition to requiring a whole new approach to our events and delivery, this also placed a new set of demands on us as a supporter and funder of work, and by way of opportunities for new work in response to the impact this health crisis had on the creative sector.

Our first and arguably most impactful intervention was a collaboration with Visual Arts Scotland (VAS), which provided paid speaking opportunities for 49 creatives drawn from across Scotland and from a wide variety of creative disciplines. VAS approached us at the outset of the first lockdown in Spring 2020 and we co-developed a series of Friday Forums, an ambitious weekly zoom-based event that brought the community together from April–June 2020 to share practice and build community. We received exceptional feedback from these events, at a time when the need for connection had never been greater and when the loss of income across the creative sector was having a devastating impact. Creative Informatics also saw a significant positive impact in subsequent funding rounds, with many creatives newer to data-driven and technical projects coming forward to explore new opportunities, having first been exposed to the programme through the Friday Forums and/or through the partnership with VAS.

Our early leadership on running online events led to the creation of an initial [Online Events Guide](#) (2020), and a specific set of training workshops for the Scottish Society of Art Historians, who were making their first move into these kinds of events. This work led to a practical [CI Toolkit for Online Events](#) (2022), which has seen significant engagement from and use by other organisations, and continues to prove useful to those planning online and hybrid work.

This move to online events saw Creative Informatics reach new audiences, particularly those who feel less able to travel, including those in more rural areas of our region; those who find it harder to travel, including those with disabilities or caring responsibilities; and, as lockdowns eased, those who were shielding for longer periods due to specific health concerns. As a result of the pivot made during lockdown, we continued to offer almost all key events in hybrid form, or with an online alternative option (e.g., for our Partnership Forums and funding workshops), developing tactics to ensure both in-person and online communities felt engaged. We have also continued to advise others on best practices for online and hybrid delivery and its importance for including diverse audiences.

Early in the Covid lockdowns Creative Informatics was part of an Una Europa-organised online hack event, bringing together students from across Europe to consider some of the challenges facing cultural organisations and cities. As a result of this engagement, which included participation by some of our partner organisations, we developed several strands of work creating paid internship opportunities for Design Informatics masters students to look at Covid-aware gallery management options for the Talbot Rice Gallery, and to explore access and experiences at the Edinburgh Fringe. The latter of which developed into a separate follow-on project with a freelance creative and a group of children with autism to explore their relationships to playful exploration of the city, particularly during the exceptionally busy August period.

Discussions with the Fruitmarket Gallery at this time also led to Creative Informatics working in partnership with them, with development expertise from the Institute for Design Informatics, to create a secure self-led mobile phone app version of their highly regarded *Night Walk for Edinburgh* piece by Janet Cardiff and George Bures Miller. *Night Walk* was first shown as part of the Edinburgh International Festival in August 2020, using loaned devices and high levels of staffing to administer loans and manage cleaning of devices, but a more flexible option was required. The Informatics-supported app addressed this challenge, working to the strict requirements of both Fruitmarket and the artists. It won the DIGITAL MEDIA: Mobile/App Design Award at the Scottish Design Awards 2021 and remains in regular use.

And finally... Back in 2020, when the Edinburgh Festivals were unable to take place in any recognisable form, Creative Informatics not only undertook research to understand the impact of this [[link to: https://theconversation.com/how-coronavirus-has-hit-the-uks-creative-industries-147396](https://theconversation.com/how-coronavirus-has-hit-the-uks-creative-industries-147396)], we also tried to bring a little Fringe magic to people wherever they were. ImprovBot [[link to: https://improvbot.ai/about/](https://improvbot.ai/about/)], the AI generated fringe programme, drawing on decades of Edinburgh Fringe data, came up with a slew of new shows, inspired new online Improverts sketches, received global press and achieved a 4-star review from The Stage.

RESEARCH

Engaging university research with Edinburgh's cultural and festival initiatives and its growing tech industry meant that we could reflect on, critique and pass on findings from our many and varied Creative Informatics activities.

The Creative Informatics project employed five full-time postdoctoral researchers, based at the University of Edinburgh and Edinburgh Napier University. From a diverse range of backgrounds, and with a wide range of skills and interests, researchers worked alongside the delivery team to help those looking for funding to formulate and articulate ideas and to conduct research on the current and evolving landscapes of the creative sector in and around Edinburgh.

From baseline mapping and surveys of the cultural landscape, to cutting-edge work on innovative new economic, pedagogical and artistic practices, Creative Informatics researchers actively engaged in leading critical research across academic disciplines as well as industrial sectors, with the aim of providing guidance and results that will have a positive impact on data-driven innovations within the creative industries, in Edinburgh/South-East Scotland and beyond, including on policy and practice. For example, our work on data ethics to support the delivery of the programme has resulted in academic research analysing and documenting aspects of data ethics facing creative practitioners, as well as a suggested framework that other institutions can reuse for managing data ethics processes and that has now been downloaded hundreds of times.

We published a range of outputs including traditional journal and conference papers but also produced white papers on a range of topics, including: documenting the digital pivot of the Fringe Festival during the 2020 pandemic; [an analysis of how best to support equality, diversity, and inclusion \(EDI\) in the creative industries](#); and an overview of how [AI is impacting the Scottish creative industries](#). These white papers allowed us to get our findings out to a broad community whilst avoiding facing the delays caused by academic publishing processes.

We also worked collaboratively on a free-to-download open access book at the close of the funded period of the programme; [Data Driven Innovation in the Creative Industries](#), edited by Melissa Terras, Vikki Jones, Nicola Osborne and Chris Speed.

Featuring many members of our community and case studies from our funded initiatives, and taking a necessarily global perspective, this collection explores the challenges and opportunities of data-driven approaches to creativity in different contexts across the arts, cultural and heritage sectors and examines how the creative industries can be supported to make best use of opportunities in digital technology and data-driven innovation.

We hope that it will provide valuable reading for those researching and studying the creative economy as well as for those who drive investment for the creative industries in a digitalised society.

Creative Informatics supported a number of larger Creative Horizon funded projects, as well as a significant number of Small Research Grants to support research activities beyond our team, across the University of Edinburgh and Edinburgh Napier University. etail of these follows.

Small Research Grants

Small grants lead to big impacts

By providing small grants of up to £5,000 to researchers at the University of Edinburgh and Edinburgh Napier University, Creative Informatics facilitated novel small-scale, early-stage research projects generating new knowledge about the creative industries. Many grant recipients used the outcomes of their research as proof-of-concept stepping stones to pursue larger follow-on programmes of research or spin-out knowledge exchange projects. These included projects like [Platform to Platform](#), a partnership with Malvern Museum of Local History translating Lorna Lloyd's WWII diaries from the page into a new podcast series, map, and digitised archive of Lloyd's diary, correspondence, photos, poetry and drawings. By analysing audience engagement with these new formats, researchers were able to answer questions about the impact and value of digitisation, which will benefit museums and archives. Hazel Hall and her co-researchers received a [British Records Association award](#) for this research.

We also funded projects exploring novel challenges with generative AI, including the film *Not I*, an artistic inquiry interrogating the ethical challenges of machine learning technologies, which was featured in the August 2023 Inspace exhibition *The Sounds of Deepfake*.

On the theme of games and immersive 3D experiences, [Digital Munya 2.0](#) is a rich VR experience of a medieval Islamic villa (Arabic munya), its landscape and authentic primary source texts and artefacts, which illuminate its historical and artistic significance. Glair Anderson, the lead researcher on *Digital Munya*, recently collaborated on a new in-game educational feature for [Assassin's Creed Mirage](#).

Creative Informatics also funded 20 small grants and 14 PhD research assistant posts. In October 2022, our small grant and PhD RA awardees participated in a joint showcase to share their work. [Read about it on the Creative Informatics research blog.](#)

Ethics

Creative Informatics had a programme-long commitment to guiding the projects we funded, as well as the wider creative community in and around Edinburgh, on best practices and thoughtful reflection on work with data and new technologies. We put this into practice through our [Creative Informatics Ethics Statement](#). We believe that taking a proactive and reflective approach to ethics from the very inception of a business or project enhances long-term business sustainability by mitigating potential ethical risks that could lead to future reputational or financial harms for creative practitioners, or societal harms for stakeholders. This is a key part of establishing integrity, trust and professionalism as a business. Every creative project and business exists within the context of a wider community and society, and it is a moral responsibility to not only comply with legislative requirements but also to consider the special role the creative industries play in shaping public understanding of ethical issues and influencing public and policy behaviour towards those concerns.

The Ethics Statement is a core part of the Creative Informatics legacy, as a means to encourage critical thinking and reflexive ethics practices among the creative industries. It could act as a template for ethics peer review, for example, or be used as a starting point for funding bodies to assess the ethics commitments and practices of companies and projects they wish to fund, including their legislative compliance around data security and information processing.

The latest version of the [Creative Informatics Ethics Statement](#) was released on 23 May 2024, with an updated self-review portion that includes a new risk register for each area. Our Ethics Statement has been identified as a worthwhile template for good practice by funding bodies in the UK's creative industries ecosystem, contributing to the development of new or evolving existing ethics statements at organisations such as the [Science Museum Group](#), a consortium of five nationally leading museums with a combined audience of over five million visitors; the CoSTAR AHRC research collaboration programme; XR Network+ EPSRC research collaboration programme; and the University of Edinburgh's College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences. The updated [Open-Access Statement](#) is hosted on Zenodo. The [original policy](#) has been downloaded over 1,000 times.

Creative Horizon Projects

Over the course of our five Creative Horizon projects, the Creative Informatics research team led forward-thinking research programmes that brought academics and industry partners together to explore what impacts emerging technologies are having, and may have in the future, for the creative industries in Edinburgh and South-East Scotland. Each team had up to £25,000 to explore the potential of emerging technologies to create new technical and business opportunities in the region.

Our research team set the theme for each Creative Horizon project, assembling partners with a wide range of complementary skills and knowledge domains to create an environment for new questions and innovative ideas to flourish.

Creative Horizon 1: Digitising ECA's Animation Archive

Edinburgh College of Art's (ECA) Animation department is home to a unique collection of student films created during the first 30 years of the programme. The objects used to make the films, including puppets and other physical archive material, are growing increasingly fragile with time. ECA Animation partnered with [Insurgent Studios](#) to develop new processes for capturing and digitising legacy student films. This included developing 3D digital models of the physical archives in both VR and AR, making a previously fragile set of assets accessible to students for exploring, experimenting and creating their own new animations for years to come.

Creative Horizon 2: Creative Cred

How can creative industries practitioners embed circular economy principles into their day-to-day working lives? [Creative Cred](#) explored this research question through the design of a mutual credit system in a partnership between researchers at the University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh Napier University and local circular economy consultancy Ostrero. Using an online network platform, Creative Cred rewards sustainable behaviour by giving circular economy credit to its members. Members can obtain Creative Cred badges to share on their own websites to demonstrate their sustainability credentials, raising awareness of circular economy principles and encouraging a more sustainable future for everyone.

Creative Horizon 3: FestForward

[FestForward](#) uses a thought-provoking fictional magazine to imagine the future of sustainable, equitable work in Scotland's festivals and broader cultural sector. This 'provotype' stimulates conversations about how we can build the future that we want for the creative industries by addressing the possible futures we might face – the good, the bad, and the ugly. Creative Informatics researchers partnered with futures consultancy Andthen to devise the fictional magazine and run a series of participatory workshops exploring festival futures with the aim of provoking policy, research and innovation which will set our festival futures on the right path.

Detecting Dark Matter Data:

data gaps for innovation and R&D activity in the creative industries

Caitlin McDonald, Creative Informatics
Jennie Jordan, Creative Research and Innovation Centre

Creative Horizon 4: There Be Dragons

This project took a data materialisation approach grounded in creative practice to investigate and untangle some of the messy issues around data and creativity, building a picture of the role that data plays in the life of the creative practitioner. The project culminated in the *There Be Dragons* exhibition at Inspace in October 2022. Individuals and collaborative groups of artists presented their work exploring the types and value of data collected about creative practitioners in the course of their professional work, as well as interrogating the role of the data that creative practitioners collect from their audiences through the products, services and experiences they provide. The exhibition was toured by creative industries policymakers and funding bodies as part of Creative Horizon 5, providing a provocative new lens with which to explore the types and value of data policymakers collect to inform their decision-making about the creative industries.

Creative Horizon 5: Detecting Dark Matter Data

Policymakers and funders for the creative industries collect and process vast amounts of data to make decisions about how to invest resources and create programmes for the creative industries. However, the data they want to use is often fragmented, difficult to access, incomplete or just plain wrong. Further, practitioners and policymakers are often at odds about the value of the data used to make policy and funding decisions. In a partnership with The Data City, researchers at Creative Informatics and the Creative Research and Innovation Centre at the University of Loughborough worked with policymakers, funders, creative practitioners and data platform providers exploring techniques to create a more unified data environment that provides value for everyone in the creative industries data ecosystem, resulting in the white paper [Detecting Dark Matter Data](#).

There Be Dragons:

EVENTS

Creative Informatics engagement activities took place throughout the programme, offering creative experiences, demonstrations, workshops and debate. Events were delivered in venues across the city, from art galleries to theatres and repurposed creative spaces, and ranged from conference-style forums to informal presentations and performances. The programme of events offered our network the opportunity to showcase their work and share research and ideas. They also provided platforms for networking and collaboration and the opportunity to engage with other creatives on a local, national and international level.

Innovation Showcase

From 2020–2023, Creative Informatics staged an annual Innovation Showcase. In 2020 this took place online and continued to grow each year before culminating in a two-day hybrid event in Central Hall in Edinburgh. Innovation Showcases were a space for the Creative Informatics community to gather and celebrate the work that was being developed through the programme and also through the wider creative industries sector in the UK.

Highlights

- ◇ An inspiring opening keynote from Leah Black on *Creativity, Communities, Funding and the Future*.
- ◇ A panel exploring the impact of the creative industries Clusters programme in Creative Catalysts featuring Prof Christopher Smith along with colleagues from other Clusters; chaired by Melissa Terras.
- ◇ Singer and producer Chagall in conversation with Edinburgh Futures Institute Director of Creative, Caroline Parkinson, before presenting *Unlocked*, an immersive light-art installation and performance.
- ◇ A special appearance from iconic artist and technology innovator Imogen Heap in conversation with author and broadcaster Gemma Cairney.

In total, there were over 800 attendances at Innovation Showcase events during the span of the Creative Informatics programme.

Creative Informatics Labs and Studios

Creative Informatics Labs were informal events that provided a meeting place for creatives of all disciplines to connect, collaborate and hear about innovative, data-driven work taking place across the creative industries. They were staged on a regular basis and proved to be hugely popular with our network.

Lab Highlights

In November 2022 we welcomed award-winning artist Rachel Maclean who had been working with the Institute for Design Informatics (IDI) to produce AI-generated audio for her new short film *Duck*, a darkly comedic British spy drama starring a deepfake Sean Connery. Rachel appeared alongside researcher and artist Martin Disley, Adam Castle (producer for *Pollyanna*) and Lynne Craig, Programme Director at the Institute of Design Informatics, who each presented work ranging from interactive digital cabaret videos to voice clones to hyper realities.

CI Lab 23: Festival Futures took place at the Biscuit Factory in April 2023 and explored the themes, ideas and methods our researchers used to produce *FestForward* magazine – a fictional, speculative magazine exploring digital and data-driven futures for Edinburgh and South-East Scotland's festivals. We were joined by Ireland's finest improvising musical comedian Abandonman, aka Rob Broderick, who presented a scratch performance inspired by *FestForward*'s imagined *Culture.ai* platform.

Creative Informatics x Edinburgh Science Festival

As we reached the end of our programme, a large-scale exhibition as part of Edinburgh Science Festival was the perfect way to showcase and celebrate the achievements of our programme participants. *Creative Informatics: Unleashing the Power of Data* ran from 20 March–9 April at the National Museum of Scotland. The exhibition featured 14 individuals and creative companies who had received funding and support from Creative Informatics including a project that used geospatial data and Python programming to turn raw data into pixel art (*Creative Gradient*, Mahsa Nikoufar) and an interactive collaborative music making app (*IMP*, Ray Interactive). Some exhibits reflected on environmental themes, with a sculpture carved with patterns reflecting data on biodiversity (*To the Core*, Kate Ives) and an action-packed VR game exploring the Scottish Highlands (*Venture's Gauntlet*, Bearhammer Games) whilst others used datasets to create striking and thought-provoking artworks such as Ploterre's *Naturally Curious*, which used environmental data to create artwork from processes and discoveries within the natural world and Caitlin McDonald and Inge Panneels' *Picture Your Poisons*, an intimate portrait of a cancer patient's journey, drawn from scientific and medical data and featuring glass casts representing treatments.

During its live dates, the exhibition reached an estimated audience of 32,000 visitors from a wide range of diverse backgrounds and demographics across the region, particularly including families with young children.

As part of the partnership with Edinburgh Science Festival, we also presented wraparound events highlighting programme participants, researchers and innovative data-driven work that is being developed in Scotland. These events reached a further 1000 ticket-buying audiences. Playable Tech's *BeatBlocks* and Dominika Jackowska's *Interactive Lightbox* were both showcased as part of the festival's opening party at City Art Centre while *Let's Play* was a dedicated late-night event that encouraged audiences to get hands-on with the latest and coolest world-leading video game tech. Guest speakers included Neil McDonnell who heads up the University of Glasgow's Museums in the Metaverse project, Brian Baglow (Scottish Games Network), Judson Cowan (Tettix Games) and Cat Burton (Vesper).

Creative AI for Creative Work brought together creative professionals working with AI to enhance their projects – from developing playful innovations to creating new revenue streams for sound and audio production. Chaired by Prof Frauke Zeller, Professor of Human-Computer Interaction and Creative Informatics at Edinburgh Napier University, the panel included Ana Betancourt (Black Goblin), Catherine Stewart (DataMind Audio) and artist Theodore Koterwas.

The Edinburgh Science Festival partnership and events generated press coverage in *The National*, *The Herald*, *The Evening News* and a feature on *STV News*, reaching even wider audiences and engaging them with the innovative and creative data-driven work generated by the Creative Informatics programme.

OUR TEAM

Creative Informatics has only been possible because of an incredible community of creatives and technologists in and around Edinburgh and South-East Scotland, as well as further afield. We would like to thank everyone we have engaged with for their immense openness and fantastic ideas and for turning these into reality, which we have been privileged to support. We know that these networks and collaborations, and the development of the ideas and their legacy, will last decades beyond this programme. We hope that this report gives some sense of the diversity and range of people we have worked with and that made the project such a success.

Our Director Melissa Terras and our Founding Director Chris Speed (now Professor of Design for Regenerative Futures at RMIT in Australia) developed a vision for Creative Informatics and have helped shape a project that is highly collaborative and open in its approach. We would like to take the opportunity here to acknowledge and thank every one of the dedicated team from across the four partner organisations who have made all of this possible and to share a little of what they will be working on next.

Firstly, thanks go to our directorate (past and present): Jarmo Eskelinen of the Data- Driven Innovation initiative; Stephen Coleman OBE of Codebase; Candace Jones of the University of Edinburgh (UoE) Business School; Caroline Parkinson from Edinburgh Innovations and Edinburgh Futures Institute (EFI); Michael Rovatsos of UoE School of Informatics and the Bayes Centre; Burkhard Schafer of UoE Law School; Michael Smyth of Edinburgh Napier University (ENU); Ola Wojtkiewicz of Creative Edinburgh; Frauke Zeller of ENU; Ritchie Somerville (now EPCC); Patricia Erskine (now EFI); Anne Sofie Laegran (UoE Research Office); Anna Votsi (EFI) and Yasmin Sulaiman (now Codebase, formerly Creative Edinburgh).

These thanks extend to everyone involved in the new projects, collaborations and organisational developments that have arisen across the partner organisations (detailed on the following pages)

At Codebase

Katherine Warren was instrumental in developing Creative Informatics whilst at Creative Edinburgh and has continued to do so at Codebase as Creative Bridge Programme Lead. Chief Bridge Strategy Officers Steven Drost and Yasmin Sulaiman (originally in her previous role at Creative Edinburgh) have both been involved since the outset, with Steven providing invaluable advice and support in the very early stages to embed the work and potential of creatives in Edinburgh thriving startup scene. Oli Littlejohn provided immense support for Creative Bridge at the start and continues to nurture the community through R&D, and Jim Newbery provided invaluable technical and startup insights in our funding processes. We would also like to thank Stephen Coleman and the whole team at Codebase, and at Techscaler, who have been unfailingly generous with their support and advice for the creatives we have worked with.

At Creative Edinburgh

Inga Dale Steyn has given us a huge amount of support and guidance as Connected Innovators Community Manager, and Zoe Alba Farrugia has provided enthusiastic support for events and highly memorable speed networking! We would like to thank Ola Wojtkiewicz and her whole team, past and present, particularly noting the early contributions of Anna Gormezano Marks (who has gone on to work with us as a freelancer), Briana Pegado, Yasmin Sulaiman (who continues to work with us in her role at Codebase) and Claire Stewart.

At Edinburgh Napier University

We would like to thank Frauke Zeller, Michael Smyth, Inge Panneels and Ingi Helgason. With special thanks to the late David Benyon for his contribution to the original proposal that went on to become Creative Informatics.

The Creative Informatics Delivery Team

The Creative Informatics Delivery Team, based at the University of Edinburgh, has been led by Programme Manager Nicola Osborne since the outset and has been supported by a huge range of talented individuals. Nicola (now managing the Institute for Design Informatics and CoSTAR Realtime Lab) would like to share huge thanks to the current team: Communications & Engagement Manager Emma Pirie (who moves to a role with the ekip project after Creative Informatics); Programme & Evaluation Officer Diane Henderson; Programme & Finance Administrator Courtney Bates (who moved full time to her parallel role at The New Real) and Research Software Engineer Evan Morgan (Design Informatics).

We would also like to thank the delivery team members who have already moved to exciting new roles: Victoria Murray (now at the Edinburgh Book Festival); Olivia Salamon (moving on to work for German Federal Government); Kam Chan (moved to the Data+Design Lab, EFI); Anna Orme (now at the Centre for Population Health Sciences); Ruth Oliver (who continues to support Creative Informatics startups and others in her role at TechScaler); Michaela Turner (who moved to a new role with Edinburgh Innovations) and Liam Upton (now at Miller Homes Ltd).

The Creative Informatics Research Team

The Creative Informatics Research Team, led by Melissa Terras, have worked closely with the delivery team to develop and deliver, as well as record and provide critical insights across, the whole programme: Suzanne Black (who has moved to the CoSTAR Foresight Lab); Chris Elsdon (now a Chancellors Fellow at UoE); Ingi Helgason (now in an ENU lecturer role); Vikki Jones and Caitlin McDonald (who have both moved to the ekip project); Inge Panneels (now in an ENU lecturer role); Susan Lechelt (now in a lecturer role at UoE) and Pip Thornton (now a Chancellors Fellow at UoE). We have also been delighted to see two of our Creative Informatics alumni, Theodore Koterwas and Martin Disley, become our colleagues at the Institute for Design Informatics at UoE, as a Lecturer and PhD student, respectively.

Additional thanks

We would like to offer additional thanks to the regular Creative Informatics collaborators who have supported delivery: Sigrid Schmeisser; Janine Matheson; Stacey Hunter; Joshua Smythe; Chris Scott; Morvern Cunningham; Tiki Muir; Amanda Tyndall; Paolo Drusi and the team at Video Production Edinburgh; Stuart Armit; Martin Baillie; Stefan Bilbao; Jessica Armstrong; Fiona Pilgrim; Sharon Pryde at Scottish Enterprise; Mark Daniels; Mark Baillie; Mark Graham; Sarah Camus and Visual Arts Scotland; Dani Trudeau at Tribe Party; Eve Equi and the Research Knowledge and Innovation (RKEI) team at the Edinburgh College of Art (ECA); Jillian Walker and Ming Cao in the ECA HR team; the Institute for Design Informatics team; the team at Edinburgh Innovations (UoE); Bright Red Triangle (ENU); Interface; Caroline Parkinson and our colleagues at the Edinburgh Futures Institute.

Finally, we would like to thank our fantastic steering board who have advised us and taken a very active role in supporting our approach and the delivery of our funding programmes by bringing their expertise to bear on selection processes. Thank you to our current chair, Sarah Prescott (UoE) and previous chair, Dorothy Miell (UoE), and to members: Rob Dobson; Barbara McKissack; James McVeigh (Festivals Edinburgh); Samantha Chadwick (BBC R&D); Clive Gillman (Creative Scotland); Peter Andras (ENU); Joanna Billingham (AHRC). We would also like to thank previous members: John Mathers (British Design Fund); Alistair Sambell (ENU); Jim Galloway (City of Edinburgh Council); Julia Amour (Festivals Edinburgh) and Joanna Littlejohns (AHRC).

CONCLUSION

Reflections and Lessons Learned

Throughout the Creative Informatics project we have been committed to learning, improving and developing what we do, and how we do it, to best achieve our aims of supporting creatives in the region to become more data driven and better able to engage with the opportunities afforded by data and technology. We did not get everything right first time – it sometimes took a lot of iteration and feedback from the community to do things better – but our sincere intention was always to do our best to support the brilliant creatives around us in the best ways possible.

We encountered two hugely impactful areas of learning that we could not have properly foreseen. Firstly, Covid fundamentally changed Creative Informatics and impacted our participants in many unexpected ways. Whilst every day in the early weeks of lockdown presented a steep learning curve, as noted earlier in this report, much of what we learnt went on to have positive lasting impacts despite the overall negative impact of Covid, particularly on those in creative roles. We did our best to use our digital expertise and resources to support the creative community of Edinburgh and its regions across this challenging period.

The second unexpected area of learning came with changes to the financial systems at the University of Edinburgh. Ongoing issues with these systems caused unacceptable delays in some payments and generated stress for the team and for our community over too long a period. Whilst we did everything within our power to speed up payments and ensure those in charge of the systems understood the deep impact of delays, we would like to acknowledge how damaging those delays were and we regret greatly the distress caused. Many will be aware that this payments issue extended far beyond Creative Informatics, but we thank our community for their grace in working with us during that period and hope that their experience of being part of the programme was more beneficial than the challenges presented by these finance challenges. This experience for participants is certainly one that we hope will never be repeated, and we note the irony that a digital technology innovation engine was so disrupted by software and data-platform issues.

The biggest lesson we have learnt is that incredible impact can be achieved when combining (relatively) modest financial investment in creative R&D projects with targeted support for the development of creative people and businesses. We now see this combination as crucial in supporting early-stage ideas and organisations as, whilst funding enables exploration and experimentation, this creates far more powerful benefits when aligned with sufficient resources to also nurture skills, reflection and most of all confidence. We can see that the impact of the increased capacity and confidence of so many of the people and organisations we have worked with will last far beyond the end of the programme, with many taking work forward with other funders, supporters and partners etc.

With five and a half years and 40 funding rounds to draw on there were plenty of opportunities to learn what we should (and shouldn't) do. As our own confidence grew, and we saw what worked best for the companies we supported, we learnt to be more flexible in our approach.

One of the earliest lessons learnt was the critically important role that providing detailed feedback plays when making funding decisions. In the first few funding rounds we knew that feedback would be important, but the relatively brief summaries we shared left some applicants frustrated and/or unclear on how to proceed. We responded to this by developing our approach to embed fuller feedback and clear next steps – which in some cases was a referral to another funder – as well as action points. We then saw applicants either directly reapply with much stronger applications, or in many cases, take up places on Creative Bridge as a result of referrals in their feedback and then reapply successfully with a much clearer idea and sense of how to make it a reality. Whilst we loved to see great ideas and strong applications at any stage, we were particularly thrilled to see applicants successful on their second, third or even fourth attempt. We have heard that for many our feedback has shifted their approach, helped them develop ideas or been valuable whether they were successfully funded or not.

For many their application to Creative Informatics was their first, or one of their first, ever funding bids, and we learnt various tactics for making the process less daunting. Whilst, with the support of our research team, we launched our first calls alongside workshops and application support, we developed these approaches over time to make these spaces more approachable and inclusive, including providing more one-to-one support for those who requested and/or needed it. We tried to make it clear that we were not trying to create hoops to jump through (no matter how long our forms looked!), but instead to support applicants to succeed, so long as their ideas fitted our eligibility criteria and had potential.

We drew on the Creative Informatics team's own experiences as funding applicants, on our learnings from early delivery of the programme and on feedback from the Creative Informatics community. We learnt, for instance, that waiting a (relatively) long time for a funding outcome caused both general anxiety and created a delay in sourcing potential alternative or accompanying funds. We switched to providing early decisions, with feedback following later, and made ourselves available to discuss feedback if/when questions arose.

One particular learning we will take forward is further consideration of how to make a fair, accountable and data-driven funding application process work in a less text-dependent format, that doesn't introduce new biases and is more accessible for applicants with neurodiversity. Whilst we have yet to find the solution, we are immensely grateful to the applicants who took time to discuss this with us and enabled us to make some valuable changes in response.

In our original plans for operating Creative Informatics we had three key governance structures: our Directorate, drawn from the core partners and meeting regularly to guide and shape the programme; our Steering Board, who provided strategic advice and met on a quarterly basis to support, guide and often 'cheerlead' for us; and our Partnership Forum, a six-monthly, town hall-format meeting that allowed the Creative Informatics community to come together and give us honest feedback on how we were doing and what they needed from us. One of our key learnings was the immense value of this latter structure and the importance of regularly being held accountable for our ambitions and approach.

These Partnership Forums allowed us to raise particular topics and questions, be honest about where our work was less strong, transparently share details on things like application rates, equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI) performance etc., and to celebrate what was working well. In exchange, the Creative Informatics community showed us great trust, kindness and patience as we dug deeper and learned how to work better, providing deeply honest comment and calling out issues/concerns or representation challenges etc.

We learnt a huge amount from the Community (e.g., via feedback forms and impact surveys) at all stages but these Partnership Forums, and the participatory formats we evolved to ensure that everyone had a voice and felt included (itself a response to feedback), showed the importance of embedding support and scaffolding, accessibility, ethics and EDI in our approach. This is something we will take with us into future projects, and we thank the Community for trusting us in this process.

We haven't mentioned specific technical or creative learnings here, but a huge amount of learning flowed in both directions between the Creative Informatics team and the Community. We learnt early on that one of our most valuable functions wasn't as a source of funding (as valued as that was) but rather our capacity to act as a trusted broker, connecting people from diverse backgrounds and practices with the ideas, projects and potential partners that could help their projects happen.

This too we will take forward, and we hope to continue connecting many in the Creative Informatics community long into the future through our follow-on projects, activities, and collaborations. Whilst the academic and delivery team brought huge expertise, so too did the creatives, early start-ups, cultural organisations and creative technologists we worked with. The resultant collaborations have been both unexpected and inspiring, and have astounded us with the vision and realisation of some truly incredible ideas.

Legacy & Impact

Our intention was always to be open and accountable in our process (embedding this ethos as a core value) and from the outset we have shared many of our key approaches, openly publishing documents and resources including our [Ethics Statement](#), [Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Policy and Action Plan](#) and [Data Management Plan](#).

It is our hope that by supporting others to learn from, reuse and remix our resources and (in the spirit of open access academic and coding practices) develop and improve them, we have made a valuable legacy contribution.

We are delighted to say that these approaches have already been taken up by others, with our ethics approach adopted by organisations including the Science Museum Group, both the ethics and EDI approaches adopted or adapted by XR Network+ and CoSTAR, and our applications process informing the BRAID responsible AI programme. We hope and anticipate that these approaches will continue to develop and prove useful to others, and we will continue to advocate both for best practices in these spaces, and for the benefit of an open and accountable approach.

Influence and Policy

The Creative Informatics team asked a lot from our funded projects: we sought a lot of data at application stage; we required ethics forms as part of contracting; we required midway and final reports as a requirement of receiving payment; and we asked for feedback on events, funding processes and participants' experience of the impact of the programme. We did this to understand our own performance, to understand the needs and shape of the community we were serving and to represent feedback on requirements, benefits and potential for R&D in the creative industries to funders, stakeholders and policy makers.

We used data from the programme (particularly from our first Impact Survey) to develop a written submission to the UK House of Lords Communication and Digital Select Committee's Creative Future Inquiry in September 2022. Our (then) Acting Director Melissa Terras also gave oral evidence in October 2022 (and appeared on Parliament TV) on the role and value of the creative industries as a place of huge innovation and potential and on the importance and impact of investment. Both written and oral evidence were cited in the final report in January 2023, with Terras quoted about the damage that Brexit has done to the cultural and creative economy.

When Creative Informatics were approached to be part of workshops led by the Design Council for the Department of Culture Media and Sport we were proud to represent our community in discussions on the role and impact of the creative industries and creatives in the wider economy. This work led to Creative Informatics being used as a case study, exemplifying the impact of the wider creative industries Cluster Programme, in the UK Government Creative Sector Vision 2030 (UK Gov 2023).

The experiences of our Community, combined with our own data on the programme and its impact, have enabled us to provide written evidence to the Scottish Government Innovation Strategy. We have also been identified as a key driver for digital economy skills in the creative industries in the EKOS report for Skills Development Scotland, "Edinburgh and South-East Scotland creative industries Cross Cutting and Sector-Specific Skills" (March 2023).

Our engagement and impact on policy has also extended beyond the UK. We have been interviewed by the Federal Research Division of the Library of Congress (USA) on our approach to outreach, creative residencies, grant programmes and data challenges; and by the Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications d'Excellence de l'Éducation Artistique et Culturelle (CMQe EAC) in Brittany, France, on the educational approach and innovation aspects of Creative Informatics, as part of a study supported by the French Ministry of Economy and Finance's "France

2030" programme. Most recently our Creative AI work has engaged with the Scottish creative community to reflect on the needs, concerns and potential for AI, and makes specific recommendations to policy makers and funders, which we hope will have a clear and valuable impact.

As Creative Informatics draws to a close, several members of the team will be carrying this work through to the EU-funded EKIP: Innovation Policy Platform for the Cultural and Creative Industries project, drawing on our data and experience to devise new mechanisms for developing policies to nurture creative and cultural innovation.

This project is connected to the €150m EIT Culture & Creativity initiative – that the University of Edinburgh is part of through Una Europa and that the team members have been part of since the bid development stage – again sharing best practices and communicating the needs of the sector back to those empowered to make change through investment.

This current work builds on the international engagement the Creative Informatics team have undertaken since the outset. This includes sharing our work and approaches and advocating for the incredible capabilities of the Scottish creative sector in meetings and presentations for visitors from: Design Beku (India); Seowipo City of Culture (South Korea); Dubai Culture and Arts Authority (UAE); policy makers and arts organisations from across Mexico; Fraunhofer MEVIS (Germany); Flickr Foundation (USA and UK); Ethereum Local (Italy); We Show Up (Canada), Ontario government (Canada); in presentations in Chengdu and in Nanjing (China); in the *FutureLab* exhibition 2020 in Shanghai (China); and through partnerships across British Council Nepal, Kathmandu University and the National Innovation Centre (Nepal), initially on the Road to COP26 project although this collaboration continues through ENU with Applied Arts Scotland.

We have always taken up opportunities to talk publicly about Creative Informatics because, even with the project drawing to a close, we believe passionately in the potential for innovation when creatives and technologists work together, when data and new technologies are used in unexpected ways and when the unique vision of creatives is applied to critical information and tech shaping our world. That sharing and embedding of learnings will continue into the future through project publications and through the individual knowledge of the Creative Informatics team and Community.

THE FUTURE

We think the most important part of Creative Informatics is and has always been the incredible creative community of Edinburgh and South East Scotland. We have been thrilled to blur the boundaries around creativity, data and technology, helping people working in these spaces to find each other and access support. This type of networking, connection, and community will be supported into the long-term through Creative Tech Scotland, a brilliant initiative from our colleagues at the Edinburgh Futures Institute (EFI). Creative Tech Scotland has already run three wonderful Annual Gatherings (with many CI alumni participating) and will be continuing into the future with an events programme to bring creatives working with data and technology together. We hope many of those who have engaged with CI will be part of these.

Over the next five years Creative Informatics' experience of working with innovative SMEs will feed into our work as part of the wide network for innovation for technology in the creative industries, as part of the £75.6m Convergent Screen Technologies and Performance in Realtime (CoSTAR), which is creating state-of-the-art research and development facilities and driving the next generation of screen technology and on-set virtual production. The programme includes a National Lab, three Network Labs and a Foresight Lab, thanks to investment from the UK Government's Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC). Creative Informatics' Director, Melissa Terras, is The University of Edinburgh CoSTAR lead on the CoSTAR Realtime Lab and the CoSTAR Foresight Lab.

Our experience of working with cultural and creative industries' SMEs and larger organisations, as well as our approach to equality, diversity and inclusion, is also feeding into the work of the new UKRI Designing Responsible Natural Language Processing Centre for Doctoral Training responsiblenlp.org, which we are delighted to have some CI alumni participating in as industry partners.

Creative Informatics' insights, and the team's expertise, is also contributing to ekip, the European Cultural and Creative Industries Policy Platform, an EU-funded project (€6m) in collaboration with 16 partners across Europe, to develop policies that support innovation for future cultural and creative industries. We hope this, alongside many of our openly licensed best practice resources, will have long term and international impact.

In addition, we continue to seek new ways to support and collaborate with creative industries SMEs and larger creative and cultural organisations. You will also see that some of our researchers and experts in both University of Edinburgh and Edinburgh Napier University working in 'Creative Informatics' as both universities now have research groups associated with this programme and the wider creative, data, and technology spaces.

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